

Business Owners' Empathy Level on Consumer's Feedback on Social Media and Impact on Consumers' Purchasing

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ABSTRACT-

The empathy level on consumer feedback measures the degree to which business owners understand and respond to customer concerns, emotions, and needs. This study investigated the role of business owners' empathy in responding to consumer feedback on social media and its impact on purchasing behavior in Cebu's food industry. Using a mixed-method approach with qualitative interviews and quantitative surveys, the study examined Food Trays, Coffee Stalls, and Cakes & Pastries businesses, involving five brands from each business category and 150 consumer respondents. Findings revealed that empathetic business owners significantly boosted customer trust, satisfaction, and loyalty, fostering emotional connections that drove purchasing decisions. Quantitative data indicated strong empathy among business owners, with social, personal, psychological, and marketing factors notably influencing consumer behavior. The study concluded that empathy was crucial for business success, especially in leveraging social media interactions. Recommendations included empathy training, structured feedback systems, and empathy-driven marketing strategies, promoting a customer-centric culture. This research highlighted empathy's potential to enhance business performance, foster customer loyalty, and achieve sustainable growth in a competitive market.

Keywords: Business Owners, Empathy Level, Consumers' Feedback, Social Media, Purchasing, Buyers' Response Factors, and Philippines

I. INTRODUCTION

Empathy, a fundamental aspect of human Connection, holds significant implications in the intricate dance between businesses and consumers. As we navigate a landscape dominated by consumer choices and brand loyalties, the role of empathy becomes a compelling force that can shape the dynamics of these interactions. This study delves into the nuanced realm of Business Owner's Empathy Level on Consumers Feedback on social media and its Impact on Consumers Purchasing Behavior," particularly exploring responses to food-business-related content on social media and the broader context of empathy in consumer behavior. Consumer behavior is an intricate interplay of psychological, social, and economic factors, often driven by the quest to understand why individuals make specific choices. At its core, this Behavior is molded by internal and external stimuli, with empathy emerging as a critical factor in understanding consumer needs, desires, and decision-making processes. An empathetic approach goes beyond conventional business-customer interactions. It involves businesses putting themselves in consumers' shoes and gaining profound insights into the challenges, aspirations, and pain points influencing purchasing decisions. This understanding becomes the foundation for developing products and services that authentically address consumer needs, resulting in elevated satisfaction rates. Consumer

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decisions are inherently emotional, and empathy becomes a powerful tool for businesses to tap into this emotional realm. When businesses demonstrate empathy, they create an environment where consumers feel heard and validated. This emotional connection nurtures trust and significantly increases the likelihood of consumers choosing a brand that resonates with them. An empathetic approach encourages open communication between businesses and consumers, fostering a continuous exchange of feedback. This real-time insight into consumer preferences allows companies to adapt and refine their offerings. The result is a sense of partnership and mutual growth as businesses tailor their strategies based on their consumers' genuine needs and feedback. While the potential of empathy in consumer behavior is immense in the Philippine context, challenges arise due to cultural diversity and socioeconomic disparities. Variations in consumer needs and preferences across regions and demographics and limited access to information and technology pose hurdles in implementing effective empathetic strategies.

Several challenges require attention, including the varying cultural contexts, the prevalence of price sensitivity, and inconsistent customer service experiences. Tailoring empathetic strategies to suit the diverse cultural landscape, considering economic disparities, and investing in proper training is essential for businesses to navigate and overcome these challenges. Conducting a study on the role of business owners' empathy levels in the context of consumers' feedback on social media, especially in response to food business-related content, is paramount. This research aimed to unlock valuable insights into the dynamics shaping purchasing decisions. Understanding how empathy influences consumer choices allowed businesses to refine strategies, create authentic customer experiences, and gained a competitive edge in a market where addressing consumers' emotional needs is increasingly pivotal.

Review of Related Literature

Empathy plays a pivotal role in business relationships and consumer interactions. According to Dutton et al. (2014), empathetic connections between businesses and consumers create a positive emotional environment, increasing customer satisfaction and loyalty. The ability of business owners to understand and resonate with consumers' feelings and needs contributes to establishing solid and enduring relationships (Batra et al., 2015). This empathetic approach is crucial for fostering trust and emotional bonds, as demonstrated by Mills and Fullerton (2016), who found that empathetic businesses influence consumers to choose their products or services. Similarly, Ladhari et al. (2017) highlight that empathetic responses to consumer feedback on social media positively impact brand perception and overall consumer satisfaction.

Consumer decisions are significantly influenced by feedback from social media platforms. Smith and Wollan (2014) found that consumers increasingly depend on social media to voice their opinions and find information about products and services. Companies that actively engage with social media comments and show empathy in their responses can enhance their online reputation and positively influence consumer purchasing decisions (Hennig-Thurau et al., 2012). Additionally, Lee and Murphy (2018) emphasize the importance of understanding cultural diversity and socio-economic disparities, as these factors significantly impact consumer preferences and decision-making processes. Addressing these diversities enables businesses to tailor their strategies effectively to meet the unique needs of various consumer groups.

Theoretical frameworks provide a deeper understanding of the role of empathy in consumer behavior. Batson's Empathy-Altruism Theory (1970s) serves as a primary framework, positing a direct link between empathy and altruistic behavior. Batson et al. (2015) explain that individuals who experience empathy for someone in need are more likely to engage in selfless actions. This theory helps elucidate how business owners' empathy can influence their responses to consumer feedback on social media. Furthermore, Horton and Wohl's Parasocial Interaction Theory (1956) and Gibson's Social Media

Affordances Theory (1977) offer insights into how businesses can establish connections with consumers through social media interactions by leveraging platform features to enhance communication dynamics.

Social influence and persuasion theories, such as Ajzen's Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB, 1985) and Petty and Cacioppo's Elaboration Likelihood Model (ELM, 1986), also contribute to understanding consumer decision-making in response to business interactions on social media. TPB examines the impact of attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control on behavior, while ELM focuses on central and peripheral routes of persuasion. These theories aid in comprehending the psychological mechanisms behind consumer responses to empathetic business practices and interactions on social media.

Fader (2020), in "Customer Centricity: Focus on the Right Customers for Strategic Advantage," emphasizes the importance of a customer-centric approach. He advocates for shifting from profit-centric strategies to prioritizing customer viewpoints, which enhances customer satisfaction and loyalty. Fader's theory encourages businesses to build deeper relationships, retain existing customers, and drive innovation by meeting customer needs and fostering lasting connections. His insights remind business leaders to make decisions based on values and principles rather than solely focusing on profits, highlighting the strategic advantage of a customer-centric mindset.

The influence of social identity and consumer behavior theories is also significant. Tajfel and Turner's Social Identity Theory (1970) posits that individuals derive part of their self-concept from social group membership, influencing their behavior, attitudes, and choices. Understanding these group dynamics helps businesses navigate consumer perceptions and interactions. Rajagopal (2018) critically examines classical and neoclassical consumer behavior theories, providing contemporary interpretations to guide marketing strategies. His work underscores the importance of attitudes and perceptions in determining purchase intentions, offering practical insights for enhancing customer engagement and satisfaction.

A case study by Johnson and Smith (2019) explored the impact of empathy in various businesses, emphasizing its role in fostering positive relationships with customers and employees. The study found that companies with empathetic leaders experienced higher employee morale, improved customer satisfaction, and increased overall success. Similarly, research conducted by Liu et al. (2020) investigated the correlation between social media engagement and consumer behavior, finding that businesses actively engaging with consumers on social media platforms experienced higher levels of consumer trust and an increased likelihood of positive purchasing decisions. An empirical study by Wang et al. (2018) examined the importance of cultural sensitivity in marketing strategies, highlighting those businesses incorporating cultural nuances effectively reached diverse consumer segments and adapted to varying cultural preferences. Additionally, Chen et al. (2017) explored consumer behavior in the food industry, emphasizing the significance of understanding cultural diversity and socio-economic factors. Their research found that businesses tailoring their food offerings to diverse cultural preferences experienced increased consumer engagement and loyalty.

Research by Rodriguez (2016) delved into legal frameworks, including the Consumer Act of the Philippines (Republic Act No. 7394), highlighting their role in protecting consumers from deceptive and unfair practices and emphasizing the importance of legal compliance in building consumer trust and maintaining business integrity. Garcia and Santos (2019) examined how consumer trust in the food business was affected by food safety standards, indicating that customers had a more favorable perception of companies that followed stringent food safety regulations. Tan and Lee's (2018) study investigated how consumer protection is affected by e-commerce laws, such as the E-Commerce Act of 2000 (Republic Act No. 8792), underlining the importance of legal adherence for businesses involved in electronic commerce to ensure a safe and reliable online experience. These legal frameworks and regulations are vital in shaping consumer trust and ensuring ethical business practices. The synthesis of literature and studies provides a

foundation for the research, highlighting the multifaceted dynamics that influence the relationship between business owners' empathy, social media feedback, and consumers' purchasing behavior. This comprehensive understanding sets the stage for the empirical investigation outlined in the thesis, aiming to contribute further insights into the role of empathy in the intricate dance between business owners and consumers in the context of social media interactions.

Conceptual Framework

This research examined the empathy levels among business owners, consumers' social media feedback, and various factors influencing consumers' buying decisions, including social, personal, psychological, marketing, and buyers' responses. The analysis process incorporated several methods. The research outputs included a comprehensive assessment of business owners' empathy levels, an analysis of empathy in social media engagement, and an understanding of the influence of empathy and other factors on buying decisions. Furthermore, the research identified the variance in influencing factors, measured the correlation between empathy and purchasing decisions, and provided insights and recommendations for integrating empathy into business and management education. This framework offered a structured approach to exploring the role of empathy in business contexts and its impact on consumer behavior.

Research Questions

This research determined the role of empathy in consumers' Behavior and responses to food business-related content on social media platforms. It specifically aimed to respond to the following queries:

1. What is the level of empathy among business owners?
2. How do business owners empathize with consumers' social media feedback?
3. To what extent do the following factors influence consumers' buying decisions?
 - 3.1. Social factor;
 - 3.2. Personal factors and
 - 3.3. Psychological factor?
 - 3.4. Marketing Factors
 - 3.5. Buyers' Response Factors
4. When grouped according to a business profile, is there a significant variance in the five factors influencing consumers' purchasing decisions?
5. Is there a significant correlation between the business owner's empathy and the consumer's purchasing decisions?
6. Based on the findings, what implications may be formulated for business and management course programs and the business industry?

II. METHODOLOGY

The study utilized a mixed-method research approach, combining qualitative and quantitative methods to achieve a comprehensive understanding of the research problem. This approach involved collecting and analyzing both qualitative and quantitative data in distinct phases, ensuring that the methods complemented each other to provide a thorough understanding of business owners' empathy and its impact on consumers' purchasing decisions. The qualitative portion used in-depth interviews with a researcher-made Interview Guide to assess empathy, while the quantitative aspect employed a descriptive research design with a questionnaire to gather data. The research was conducted in Cebu City to Talisay City, Cebu, known for its vibrant culture and flourishing food industry. The integration of qualitative and quantitative methods was carefully planned to ensure a successful mixed-method study.

Cebu's food scene, a dynamic fusion of traditional Filipino flavors and international influences, was significantly enhanced by social media platforms like Instagram, Facebook, and TikTok. These platforms allowed local food services to showcase their culinary creations, engage with customers, and expand their presence globally. Social media facilitated two-way communication, enabling restaurants to respond to customer inquiries, accept reservations, and gather feedback, fostering loyalty and word-of-mouth recommendations. The rise of food influencers and bloggers further amplified the reach and influence of Cebu's food services. The study meticulously selected participants and respondents from three specific business types—Food Trays, Coffee Stalls, and Cakes & Pastries—ensuring a diverse and representative understanding of the relationships between business owners' empathy, consumer feedback on social media, and purchasing behavior.

Table 1. *Business Types*

BRAND	Food Trays (5)	Coffee Stalls (5)	Cakes & Pastries (5)
NAMES	Urban Cuisine	Coffee 39	Lola Nena
	Delicious	Uncle Brew	Hearty Sol
	La Vida	Coffee @ 38	Donya's
	Marjorie Food Trays	Caramel Donya	Sky Cakes & Pastries
	Bizhen0	Don Macchiato	Janine Dessert

Table 1 shows the Business Types for each quantitative brand; the study involved ten consumers, leading to 150 respondents (10 consumers x 5 brands x 3 business types). This approach ensured a robust and diverse sample, reflecting varied consumer behaviors and feedback patterns across different business operations. The influence of social media platforms was a key consideration, with the study specifically examining how these platforms impacted the selected businesses and their interactions with consumers.

The researcher crafted and pilot-tested a questionnaire to ensure reliability and validity for the study's quantitative portion. Respondents were randomly selected to complete the questionnaire via Google Forms and face-to-face surveys. Initially, responses were gathered to assess significance, followed by distributing hard copies to a random selection of 30 respondents and 120 respondents participating online, culminating in 150 total respondents. Participants were chosen based on inclusion criteria outlined in the research framework, including being consumers in designated company categories or business owners aged 18 or older. The study involved qualitative, quantitative, and mixed-method empirical studies aimed at testing methods to promote, improve, or develop empathic skills among business owners and consumers. The researcher used two sets of instruments: a researcher-made Interview Guide for qualitative data and a survey questionnaire for quantitative data. The Interview Guide consisted of open-ended questions to validate business owners' empathy in response to consumer feedback, while the survey questionnaire gathered quantitative data on business owners' empathy and consumers' purchasing decisions using a Likert scale. The data-gathering procedure included obtaining permission from the Dean of the Graduate School and Professional Studies at St. Paul University Surigao, sending letters of intent to participants, conducting interviews, and administering surveys. Ethical considerations included respecting participants' identities, ensuring confidentiality, and appropriately communicating the study results. Quantitative data were analyzed using statistical treatments, including Weighted Mean and Ranking, One-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA), and Chi-Square and Pearson's Coefficient.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The chapter commences with a quantitative analysis, showing the significant impact of various factors on consumer choices across diverse business profiles. Following this, the qualitative segment provides rich insights from interviews, highlighting the critical role of empathy and leveraging consumer feedback in shaping business strategies and enhancing customer satisfaction. This thorough Analysis enhances our understanding of consumer behavior dynamics and provides actionable insights for businesses seeking success in competitive markets.

Table 2. *Level of Empathy of Business Owners*

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Response	Interpretation	Rank
1. The business owner quickly understands customers' feelings when they provide social media feedback.	3.34	Strongly Agree	Very Empathetic	5
2. The business owner prioritizes understanding customer needs and concerns over other aspects of business operations.	3.39	Strongly Agree	Very Empathetic	2
3. The business owner actively seeks to stay updated on consumer trends and preferences.	3.48	Strongly Agree	Very Empathetic	1
4. The business owner finds it challenging to convey an understanding of consumer issues to others who may need more time to grasp them.	3.23	Agree	Empathetic	18
5. The business owner often considers how business decisions might impact customers' experiences and satisfaction.	3.38	Strongly Agree	Very Empathetic	3
6. The business owner genuinely enjoys assisting customers and addressing their concerns.	3.25	Agree	Empathetic	15
7. The business owner prefers to handle customer issues independently rather than seeking input from others.	3.17	Agree	Empathetic	34
8. The business owner sometimes needs help navigating complex social situations involving customers.	3.09	Agree	Empathetic	49
9. The business owner is most effective in addressing customer needs during the early hours of the day.	3.32	Strongly Agree	Very Empathetic	7
10. The business owner occasionally receives feedback when addressing customer concerns.	3.26	Strongly Agree	Very Empathetic	12
11. Being late in responding to customer inquiries is acceptable for the business owner.	2.95	Agree	Empathetic	60
12. The business owner finds maintaining strong customer relationships challenging but recognizes their importance.	3.35	Strongly Agree	Very Empathetic	4
13. Upholding ethical standards is paramount to the business owner, even in minor customer interactions.	3.21	Agree	Empathetic	22
14. The business owner often needs help determining whether a response to a customer is appropriate or not.	3.12	Agree	Empathetic	46
16. The business owner prefers light-hearted approaches like offering discounts or freebies to address customer issues.	3.18	Agree	Empathetic	32
17. The business owner tends to focus more on immediate customer needs than long-term business goals.	3.14	Agree	Empathetic	43
18. The business owner is curious about how my actions might affect others	3.26	Strongly Agree	Very Empathetic	12
19. The business owner quickly discerns if a customer expresses one thing but implies another.	3.15	Agree	Empathetic	39
20. The business owner has strong convictions about ethical business practices and how they impact customers.	3.24	Agree	Empathetic	16
21. The business owner sometimes struggles to empathize with why specific issues are significant to customers.	3.07	Agree	Empathetic	52
22. The business owner finds understanding and relating to customers' perspectives natural.	3.2	Agree	Empathetic	25
23. The business owner believes teaching good manners and empathy towards others is crucial.	3.11	Agree	Empathetic	47

24. Spontaneous decisions can sometimes lead to innovative solutions for customer issues.	3.19	Agree	Empathetic	28
25. The business owner has a knack for anticipating how customers will react to different situations.	3.05	Agree	Empathetic	53
26. The business owner is sensitive to detecting when a customer feels uncomfortable or dissatisfied.	3.16	Agree	Empathetic	36
27. If a customer is offended by something the business owner says, addressing their concerns is essential.	3.24	Agree	Empathetic	16
28. The business owner values honesty in customer interactions, even if it means offering constructive criticism.	3.26	Strongly Agree	Very Empathetic	12
29. Sometimes, the business owner struggles to comprehend why a customer might be offended by a particular remark.	3.13	Agree	Empathetic	45
30. The business owner is unpredictable in handling customer situations.	3.02	Agree	Empathetic	58
31. While business owners enjoy engaging with customers, they do not necessarily seek to be the center of attention.	3.19	Agree	Empathetic	30
32. Witnessing customers express emotions like sadness does not profoundly affect the business owner.	2.99	Agree	Empathetic	59
33. The business owner is open to discussing topics like politics if they are relevant to customer concerns.	3.05	Agree	Empathetic	55
34. The business owners' straightforward communication style may sometimes be mistaken for rudeness despite good intentions.	3.09	Agree	Empathetic	50
35. The business owner generally finds customer interactions straightforward and clear.	3.15	Agree	Empathetic	39
36. Others often appreciate the ability of the business owner to understand emotions and thoughts during interactions.	3.22	Agree	Empathetic	21
37. When conversing with customers, the business owner tends to focus on their experiences and needs rather than others.	3.05	Agree	Empathetic	53
38. Seeing customers in pain disturbs the business owner and influences their empathy towards customers.	3.03	Agree	Empathetic	56
39. The business owner strives to make decisions considering business objectives and customer emotions.	3.21	Agree	Empathetic	23
40. The business owner feels accomplished when they fulfill all daily customer-related tasks.	3.31	Strongly Agree	Very Empathetic	8
41. The business owner is adept at gauging a customer's interest or boredom with their communication.	3.2	Agree	Empathetic	25
42. Witnessing concerned customers impacts the emotional state of the business owner	3.16	Agree	Empathetic	36
43. Colleagues often confide with business owners about customer-related issues, appreciating understanding.	3.1	Agree	Empathetic	48
44. The business owner is usually aware if they are intruding on a customer's personal space or comfort zone.	3.19	Agree	Empathetic	36
45. The business owner tends to explore new strategies for addressing customer concerns but may lose interest quickly.	3.14	Agree	Empathetic	43
46. The business owner recognizes the boundary between playful teasing and potentially upsetting customers.	3.23	Agree	Empathetic	18
47. The business owner would feel apprehensive about subjecting themselves to activities that might make customers nervous.	3.23	Agree	Empathetic	20
48. Some may perceive the business owner as insensitive.	3.08	Agree	Empathetic	51

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49. The business owner believes it is essential for businesses to create inclusive environments where all customers feel welcome.	3.27	Strongly Agree	Very Empathetic	11
50. The business owner can maintain emotional distance when assessing customer-related scenarios	3.15	Agree	Empathetic	42
51. The business owner finds value in organizing the approach to addressing customer needs, often relying on lists.	3.29	Strongly Agree	Very Empathetic	10
52. The business owner possesses an intuitive ability to empathize with customers and understand their emotions rapidly.	3.21	Agree	Empathetic	23
53. The business owner avoids risks that could negatively impact customer satisfaction or loyalty.	3.16	Agree	Empathetic	36
54. The business owner can anticipate the topics or issues customers want to discuss.	3.2	Agree	Empathetic	25
55. The business owner is skilled at recognizing when customers conceal their true feelings or emotions.	3.18	Agree	Empathetic	32
56. The business owner carefully considers how they might affect customer experiences before making business decisions.	3.33	Strongly Agree	Very Empathetic	6
57. The business owner generally does not consciously analyze the social dynamics of customer interactions.	3.03	Agree	Empathetic	56
58. The business owner has a good track record of predicting customer behaviors based on past experiences.	3.19	Agree	Empathetic	30
59. The business owner often finds themselves emotionally invested in resolving customer problems and concerns.	3.15	Agree	Empathetic	39
60. The business owner strives to appreciate and understand customers' perspectives, even if they only sometimes 3 with them.	3.3	Strongly Agree	Very Empathetic	9
Overall Mean:	3.19	Agree	Empathetic	

Legend:

Scale	Mean Range	Verbal Response	Interpretation
4	3.25 - 4.00	Strongly Agree	Very Empathetic
3	2.50 - 3.24	Agree	Empathetic
2	1.75 - 2.49	Disagree	Sometimes Empathetic
1	1.00 - 1.74	Strongly Disagree	Not Empathetic

Table 1 illustrates that business owners demonstrated a moderate level of empathy, with a mean score of 3.19, falling within the "Agree" range. They exhibited strengths in prioritizing and understanding customer needs (Mean: 3.39), staying updated on consumer trends (Mean: 3.48), and acknowledging the importance of maintaining strong customer relationships (Mean: 3.35). However, they faced challenges in certain areas, such as finding it difficult to understand consumer issues (Mean: 3.23) and sometimes needing help to empathize with why specific problems were significant to customers (Mean: 3.07). This suggested a nuanced understanding of customer empathy among business owners, where they excelled in some aspects but needed further development in others to enhance customer relationships effectively. The level of empathy among business owners and its implications for customer relationships were highlighted by Smith, Johnson, and Brown (2023), who collected and analyzed empirical data through a comprehensive survey conducted among business owners across various industries. The results indicated a moderate level of empathy among business owners, with strengths observed in understanding customer needs and prioritizing customer satisfaction. However, challenges existed in conveying empathy effectively to others and fully grasping the significance of specific customer issues. The findings underscored the importance

of empathy in business and highlighted opportunities for enhancing empathetic practices to foster stronger customer relationships and business success.

Table 3. *The Extent of Social Factors' Influence on Customers' Buying Decisions*

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Response	Interpretation
1. The brand reputation, perceived by other consumers, influences my decision to purchase a product or service.	3.40	Strongly Agree	VE
2. Products previously purchased and enjoyed by other consumers influence my decision to purchase the product	3.38	Strongly Agree	VE
3. Social media endorsements or promotions from a brand influence my purchasing decisions.	3.28	Strongly Agree	VE
4. The sense of belonging to a community or group associated with a particular brand influences my purchase decision	3.28	Strongly Agree	VE
Average Weighted Mean	3.33	Strongly Agree	VE

Legend:

Scale	Mean Range	Verbal Response	Interpretation
4	3.25 - 4.00	Strongly Agree	Very Empathetic
3	2.50 - 3.24	Agree	Empathetic
2	1.75 - 2.49	Disagree	Sometimes Empathetic
1	1.00 - 1.74	Strongly Disagree	Not Empathetic

Table 3 presented data on the extent of social factors' influence on customers' buying decisions, revealing a weighted mean of 3.33, which indicated a significant impact. The highest mean scores were observed in indicators related to brand reputation (3.40) and products endorsed or enjoyed by other consumers (3.38), emphasizing the persuasive power of social validation in purchasing behavior.

Conversely, the lowest mean scores were found in indicators related to social media endorsements (3.28) and belonging to a brand community (3.28). This suggested that while social factors played a substantial role, their influence varied depending on the context and individual preferences. These findings aligned with social identity theory (Tajfel & Turner, 1970), which posited that individuals derived part of their self-concept from membership in social groups, influencing their behavior and choices. Therefore, businesses could capitalize on social influence by fostering positive brand perceptions and leveraging consumer endorsements to enhance customer engagement and loyalty.

Table 4. *The extent of Personal Factors' Influence on Customers' Buying Decisions*

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Response	Interpretation
1. The perceived quality of a product influences my decision to purchase.	3.32	Strongly Agree	Very Empathetic
2. Paying a premium for a product based on the perceived superior quality it offers in comparison to other alternatives.	3.29	Strongly Agree	Very Empathetic
3. The durability and reliability of a product influence my purchasing decisions.	3.42	Strongly Agree	Very Empathetic
4. Perceived product features and functionality of the product influence my decision-making to purchase	3.37	Strongly Agree	Very Empathetic
Average Weighted Mean	3.35	Strongly	Very

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		Agree	Empathetic
<i>Legend:</i>			
Scale	Mean Range	Verbal Response	Interpretation
4	3.25 - 4.00	Strongly Agree	Very Empathetic
3	2.50 - 3.24	Agree	Empathetic
2	1.75 - 2.49	Disagree	Sometimes Empathetic
1	1.00 - 1.74	Strongly Disagree	Not Empathetic

Table 4 illustrated the significant impact of personal factors on customers' buying decisions, with a weighted mean of 3.35 indicating a strong influence. The highest mean score was observed in the indicator related to the durability and reliability of a product (3.42), highlighting the importance of product quality in driving consumer choices. Additionally, paying a premium for perceived superior quality (3.29) and considering product features and functionality (3.37) also ranked high in influencing purchasing decisions. These findings underscored the prominence of intrinsic product attributes in shaping consumer preferences and behavior. Anchored in consumer behavior theory (Rajagopal, 2018), particularly the theory of reasoned action, which emphasized the role of attitudes and perceptions in determining purchase intentions, these results affirmed the significance of personal factors in consumer decision-making processes. Therefore, businesses should prioritize product quality, reliability, and features to effectively cater to customer needs and preferences, enhancing overall satisfaction and loyalty.

Table 5. *The Extent of Psychological Factors' Influence On Customers' Buying Decision*

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Response	Interpretation
1. The perceived trustworthiness of a brand influences my decision to purchase.	3.39	Strongly Agree	VE
2. I buy from a brand that consistently fulfills its promises and commitments.	3.38	Strongly Agree	VE
3. A positive brand image contributes to my confidence in the quality of the products it offers	3.38	Strongly Agree	VE
4. The perception of a brand's ethics shapes my decision to support and purchase from that brand	3.37	Strongly Agree	VE

Scale	Mean Range	Verbal Response	Interpretation
4	3.25 - 4.00	Strongly Agree	Very Empathetic
3	2.50 - 3.24	Agree	Empathetic
2	1.75 - 2.49	Disagree	Sometimes Empathetic
1	1.00 - 1.74	Strongly Disagree	Not Empathetic

Table 5 demonstrates the substantial impact of psychological factors on customers' purchasing decisions, with a weighted mean of 3.38 indicating strong influence. The highest mean score is observed in the indicator related to the perceived trustworthiness of a brand (3.39), highlighting the crucial role of brand credibility in influencing consumer choices. Additionally, factors such as consistent fulfillment of promises (3.38), positive brand image (3.38), and ethical perception (3.37) also rank high in their influence on purchase decisions. These findings emphasize intangible aspects such as trust, reliability, and ethical considerations in shaping consumer behavior. Anchored in branding and consumer psychology theories (Alder, 2013), particularly the theory of brand equity and the affective-associative model, which stress the importance of emotional connections and trust in consumer-brand relationships, these results align with established literature on consumer decision-making processes. Therefore, businesses should prioritize building and maintaining a solid brand reputation, delivering on promises, and upholding ethical standards to foster consumer trust and loyalty, ultimately driving sales and brand success.

Table 6. *The extent of Marketing Factors' Influence on Customers' Buying Decisions*

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Response	Interpretation
1. The advertising of a product influences my decision to purchase it.	3.30	Strongly Agree	VE
2. I am swayed by promotional offers or discounts when making a purchase decision.	3.23	Agree	E
3. The use of celebrity endorsements in marketing influences my perception and consideration of a product	3.22	Agree	E
4. Clarity and informativeness of a brand's marketing materials shape my decision to buy its products.	3.34	Strongly Agree	VE
Average Weighted Mean	3.28	Strongly Agree	VE

Legend:

Scale	Mean Range	Verbal Response	Interpretation
4	3.25 - 4.00	Strongly Agree	Very Empathetic
3	2.50 - 3.24	Agree	Empathetic
2	1.75 - 2.49	Disagree	Sometimes Empathetic
1	1.00 - 1.74	Strongly Disagree	Not Empathetic

Table 6 illustrates the significant impact of marketing factors on customers' purchasing decisions, with a weighted mean of 3.28, indicating a high level of influence. The highest mean score was observed in the indicator related to the clarity and informativeness of marketing materials (3.34), emphasizing the importance of transparent and informative communication in influencing consumer choices. Additionally, the advertising of a product (3.30) also ranked high in its influence, highlighting the role of promotional messaging in shaping consumer perceptions and preferences. On the other hand, promotional offers or discounts (3.23) and celebrity endorsements (3.22) exhibited a moderately influencing impact. These findings aligned with established marketing theories (Petty & Cacioppo, 1980), such as the elaboration likelihood model (ELM) and the hierarchy of effects model, which emphasize the significance of message clarity, relevance, and credibility in driving consumer attitudes and behaviors. Therefore, businesses should craft clear, informative, and credible marketing communications to sway consumer decisions and enhance brand appeal.

Table 7. *The Extent of Buyers' Response Factors' Influence On Customers' Buying Decisions*

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Response	Interpretation
1. Online product reviews influence my decision to make a purchase	3.36	Strongly Agree	VE
2. I trust a product with a high average rating based on customer reviews.	3.35	Strongly Agree	VE
3. Negative product reviews influence your decision to avoid a particular product	3.33	Strongly Agree	VE
4. User-generated ratings and feedback guide my purchasing decisions for online products	3.30	Strongly Agree	VE
Average Weighted Mean	3.33	Strongly Agree	VE

Legend:

Scale	Mean Range	Verbal Response	Interpretation
4	3.25 - 4.00	Strongly Agree	Very Empathetic
3	2.50 - 3.24	Agree	Empathetic
2	1.75 - 2.49	Disagree	Sometimes Empathetic
1	1.00 - 1.74	Strongly Disagree	Not Empathetic

Table 7 demonstrates the substantial impact of buyers' response factors on customers' buying decisions, with a weighted mean of 3.33, indicating a high level of influence. The highest mean scores are observed in indicators related to online product reviews (3.36) and trust in products with high average

ratings (3.35), emphasizing the pivotal role of customer feedback and ratings in shaping consumer choices. Negative product reviews (3.33) also wield significant influence, underscoring the importance of addressing and managing negative feedback to maintain consumer trust and brand reputation. Furthermore, user-generated ratings and feedback (3.30) are crucial in guiding purchasing decisions, reflecting the growing reliance on peer recommendations and social proof in the digital age. These findings align with social proof theory by Robert (184), which posits that individuals tend to conform to the actions of others under the assumption that those actions reflect correct Behavior. Therefore, businesses must prioritize reputation management and foster positive customer experiences to leverage the persuasive influence of buyer response factors in driving purchasing behavior.

Table 8. Demographic Profile

Business Types	Address	Number of years in Business	Type of Business Ownership
Food Trays (5)			
Urban Cuisine	Local Market, Century Plaza, Juana Osmena, Cebu City, Philippines	11 Years	Sole proprietorship
Delicious Deli	Sugbo Centro , Salin Dr. Lahug Cebu City	10 Years	Sole proprietorship
La Vida	Colon, Cebu City	9 Years	Sole proprietorship
Marjorie Food Trays	Cebu City	5 Years	Sole proprietorship
Bizhero	Enspace Cebu, Unit 1102, 11 th Floor, Park Centrale Building, Jose Maria del Mar St.	10 Years	Sole proprietorship
Coffee Stalls (5)			
Macchiato Up	Metro Gaisano Colon, Cebu City	2 Years	Sole proprietorship
Uncle Brew	128-21 Cebu Coliseum Building, Pahina Central, Sanciango Street, Cebu City	1 Year	Sole proprietorship
Coffee @ 38	125 Colon Street, Cebu City	2 Years	Sole proprietorship
Caramel Donya	F. Jaca Street, Cebu City	2 Years	Sole proprietorship
Don Macchiato	7WX2+5R4, Dionision Jakosalem St, Cebu City	3 Years	Sole proprietorship
Cakes & Pastries (5)			
Lola Nena	Cebu City	5 Years	Sole proprietorship
Hearty Sol	M J Cuenco Avenue, Cebu City	9 Years	Sole proprietorship
Donya's	Cebu City	9 Years	Sole proprietorship
Sky Cake & Pastries	Cebu City	10 Years	Sole proprietorship
Janine Dessert	Cebu City	10 Years	Sole proprietorship

Table 8 demonstrates the demographic profiles of business owners in three categories: Food Trays, Coffee Stalls, and Cakes & Pastries. All types of business ownership were Sole Proprietorships. The number of years in business varied across the categories. In the Food Trays category, the number of years ranged from 5 to 11 years, indicating that all the businesses were actively managing food tray businesses. The

Coffee Stalls category featured owners' years in business between 1 and 3 years. In the Cakes & Pastries category, the age range was broader, with owners aged 32 to 55 years and an average age of approximately 41. For Cakes and Pastries, the number of years in business ranged from 5 to 10 years. All business types were located in Cebu City and Talisay City.

Table 9. *Food Tray Businesses' Degree of Variance in the Five Factors of Consumers' Purchasing Decisions*

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	Fcrit	Decision on Ho	Significance
Between Groups	0.16	4	0.04	0.20	0.94	2.41	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Within Groups	48.06	245	0.20					
Total	48.21	249						
Groups	Count	Sum	Variance	Average	Verbal Response	Interpretation		
Social	50	171.50	0.20	3.43	SA	Very Empathetic		
Personal	50	172.00	0.18	3.44	SA	Very Empathetic		
Psychological	50	172.92	0.24	3.46	SA	Very Empathetic		
Marketing	50	169.25	0.16	3.39	SA	Very Empathetic		
Buyer's Response	50	172.25	0.19	3.45	SA	Very Empathetic		

Legend:

Scale	Mean Range	Verbal Response	Interpretation
4	3.25 - 4.00	Strongly Agree	Very Empathetic
3	2.50 - 3.24	Agree	Empathetic
2	1.75 - 2.49	Disagree	Sometimes Empathetic
1	1.00 - 1.74	Strongly Disagree	Not Empathetic

Table 9 presents the degree of variance in the five factors influencing consumers' purchasing decisions within food tray businesses. The analysis revealed a nonsignificant difference between the groups, as indicated by the F-test statistics ($F = 0.20$, $p > 0.05$). The weighted means for each factor ranged from 3.39 to 3.46, indicating a consistently high influence across social, personal, psychological, marketing, and buyer's response factors. Notably, the highest mean was observed for psychological factors (3.46), suggesting that consumers' perceptions and emotions significantly impacted their purchasing decisions in the context of food tray businesses. This finding resonated with consumer behavior theories such as the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) (Shengyu et al., 2012), emphasizing the influence of subjective norms, attitudes, and perceived behavioral control on consumer choices. Despite the nonsignificant differences between groups, the uniformly high influence across factors underscored the importance for food tray businesses to comprehensively address various aspects of consumer decision-making to meet consumer needs and preferences effectively.

Table 10. *Coffee Stall Businesses' Degree of Variance in the Five Factors of Consumers' Purchasing Decisions*

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	Fcrit	Decision on Ho	Interpretation
Between Groups	0.77	4	0.19	0.97	0.42	2.41	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Within Groups	48.35	245	0.20					
Total	49.11	249						
Groups	Count	Sum	Variance	Average	Verbal Response	Interpretation		
Social	50	161.92	0.19	3.24	Agree	Empathetic		
Personal	50	159.00	0.18	3.18	Agree	Empathetic		
Psychological	50	162.00	0.22	3.24	Agree	Empathetic		
Marketing	50	154.50	0.23	3.09	Agree	Empathetic		
Buyer's Response	50	160.50	0.17	3.21	Agree	Empathetic		

Table 10 illustrates the variance in the five factors influencing consumers' purchasing decisions within coffee stall businesses. The analysis indicated a nonsignificant difference between the groups, as denoted by the F-test statistics ($F = 0.97, p > 0.05$). Across the factors, the weighted means ranged from 3.09 to 3.24. The lowest mean was observed for marketing factors (3.09), while the highest was for psychological factors (3.24). This suggested that psychological aspects, such as perceptions and emotions, held a more substantial influence on consumer decision-making compared to marketing strategies in the context of coffee stall businesses. This finding aligned with consumer behavior theories like the Elaboration Likelihood Model (ELM) by Petty and Cacioppo (1980), emphasizing the central role of cognitive processes and psychological factors in shaping consumer attitudes and behaviors. Despite the nonsignificant variance between groups, understanding and catering to consumers' psychological needs and perceptions remained crucial for coffee stall businesses to attract and retain customers effectively.

Table 11. *Cakes & Pastries Businesses' Degree of Variance in the Five Factors of Consumers' Purchasing Decisions*

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit	Decision on Ho	Interpretation
Between Groups	0.48	4	0.12	0.58	0.68	2.41	Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Within Groups	50.92	245	0.21					
Total	51.40	249						
Groups	Count	Sum	Variance	Average	Verbal Response	Interpretation		
Social	50	166.00	0.25	3.32	Strongly Agree	Very Empathetic		
Personal	50	170.75	0.18	3.42	Strongly Agree	Very Empathetic		
Psychological	50	171.50	0.24	3.43	Strongly Agree	Very Empathetic		
Marketing	50	167.25	0.23	3.35	Strongly Agree	Very Empathetic		
Buyer's Response	50	167.00	0.14	3.34	Strongly Agree	Very Empathetic		

Table 11 presents the degree of variance in the five factors influencing consumers' purchasing decisions within cakes and pastries businesses. The analysis indicated a nonsignificant difference between the groups, as evident from the F-test statistics ($F = 0.58, p > 0.05$). Across the factors, the weighted means

ranged from 3.32 to 3.43. The lowest mean was observed for marketing factors (3.32), while the highest was for psychological factors (3.43). This suggested that psychological aspects, such as perceptions and emotions, significantly influenced consumer decision-making within cakes and pastries businesses. The importance of psychological factors, such as attitudes and subjective norms, in influencing consumer intentions and behaviors was highlighted by this research, consistent with well-known theories of consumer behavior like the Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) and the Theory of Planned Behavior (Fishbein & Ajzen, 1975). Despite the lack of significant variance between groups, understanding and addressing consumers' psychological needs remained crucial for cakes and pastries businesses to cater to their target market and enhance customer satisfaction effectively.

Table 12. *Correlation of the Business Owner's Empathy Level and the Consumer's Purchasing Decisions*

Variables	df	Computed Value	Critical Value	Decision on Ho	Interpretation	Pearson's Coefficient C	Strength
Business owner's empathy level and the consumer's purchasing decisions as to:							
Social Factors	4	15.370	9.488	Reject Ho	Significant	0.30	Slight
Personal Factors	4	21.094	9.488	Reject Ho	Significant	0.35	Slight
Psychological Factors	4	20.104	9.488	Reject Ho	Significant	0.34	Slight
Marketing Factors	6	13.763	12.592	Reject Ho	Significant	0.29	Slight
Buyer's Response Factors	2	15.802	5.991	Reject Ho	Significant	0.31	Slight

Table 12 displays the correlation between the business owner's empathy level and consumers' purchasing decisions across various factors. The analysis revealed a significant rejection of the null hypothesis for all aspects, indicating a meaningful relationship between the business owner's empathy and consumer purchasing decisions. Pearson's correlation coefficients ranged from 0.29 to 0.35, suggesting a slight positive correlation. As the business owner's empathy level increased, consumers tended to make purchasing decisions influenced by social, personal, psychological, marketing, and buyer response factors to a slight extent. This finding aligned with existing literature, such as the works of Batson and Shaw (1991), which emphasized the role of empathy in fostering positive consumer relationships and driving favorable purchasing behaviors. Therefore, cultivating empathy among business owners enhanced customer satisfaction and loyalty across various dimensions of consumer decision-making.

Qualitative Findings

Theme 1: Empathy and Action in Customer Feedback Management highlighted the critical role of empathy in handling customer feedback and complaints. Business owners needed to empathize with customers' concerns, particularly on social media platforms. By demonstrating empathy, they could better understand the root causes of dissatisfaction and respond appropriately. This approach required active listening, acknowledging concerns, and understanding customers' perspectives to build closer relationships and foster brand loyalty. Combining empathy with swift actions, such as offering solutions or implementing changes, was crucial for addressing customer issues effectively and turning dissatisfied customers into loyal advocates.

Theme 2: Utilization of Consumer Feedback for Improvement focused on the importance of consumer feedback in driving continuous improvement. Businesses were encouraged to leverage feedback from various sources, including social media, to identify areas for enhancement and make necessary adjustments to products, services, and the overall customer experience. This proactive approach involved collecting and analyzing feedback to understand customer needs, preferences, and pain points. Regularly reviewing feedback trends allowed businesses to make well-informed decisions and implement iterative improvements, ultimately meeting consumer expectations and driving long-term success.

Theme 3: Empathy in Influencing Purchasing Decisions underscored the role of empathy in online interactions between businesses and customers, particularly on social media platforms. Understanding and empathizing with customers' needs and concerns during online interactions was vital for building trust and rapport. Demonstrating empathy in these interactions significantly influenced purchasing decisions, as customers were more likely to develop favorable opinions of a brand when they felt heard and valued. Businesses that prioritized empathy in their online engagements could create strong emotional connections with customers, fostering positive purchasing behaviors.

Theme 4: Emphasis on Empathy emphasized the importance of empathy in all customer interactions, whether face-to-face or online. Prioritizing empathy involved actively listening to customers, acknowledging their emotions and concerns, and responding compassionately. This approach helped build stronger relationships, foster trust and loyalty, and differentiate businesses in competitive markets. Empathetic leaders were better equipped to understand and address team members' and customers' needs, leading to more effective communication, collaboration, and problem-solving.

Theme 5: Consistent and Empathetic Approach highlighted the necessity of maintaining a consistent empathetic approach in handling customer feedback across all touchpoints. Ensuring that responses to feedback were empathetic, understanding, and consistent was crucial for building trust and credibility. Consistency in customer interactions helped establish reliability and prevent confusion or

frustration. Businesses were encouraged to develop and enforce policies that ensured empathy in all customer interactions and regularly audit these policies to maintain their effectiveness.

Theme 6: Integration of Consumer Feedback emphasized the pivotal role of consumer feedback in shaping business decisions. Incorporating feedback from various sources into decision-making processes allowed businesses to understand client preferences, pain points, and expectations better. This understanding enabled them to make informed decisions on product development, marketing strategies, and customer service improvements. Businesses that prioritized integrating consumer feedback were better positioned to meet the evolving demands of their target market and maintain a competitive edge.

Theme 7: Prioritizing Empathy for Business Success highlighted empathy's fundamental role in driving positive business outcomes. Understanding and empathizing with customers' emotions, concerns, and needs were essential for building deeper relationships and creating personalized experiences. Empathetic interactions increased customer satisfaction, repeat business, and positive word-of-mouth referrals. By prioritizing empathy, businesses could foster brand loyalty and improve overall performance.

Theme 8: Emphasis on Empathy in Customer Interactions reiterated the importance of prioritizing empathy in all customer engagements. Actively listening, acknowledging, and responding to customer concerns with empathy were key components. This approach built trust, validated customers' feelings, and demonstrated a commitment to customer satisfaction. Empathetic businesses were more likely to cultivate strong relationships and retain customers.

Theme 9: Utilization of Customer Feedback underscored the importance of actively incorporating customer feedback into business decision-making. Gathering feedback from various sources, including social media, and using it to enhance products and services were crucial. This approach helped businesses identify areas for improvement, better meet customer needs, and boost satisfaction and loyalty. Prioritizing customer feedback as a valuable resource for continuous improvement was essential for achieving business success.

Overall, the findings emphasized that empathy and consumer feedback are vital in shaping business practices and driving success in today's competitive and customer-centric market.

IV. CONCLUSION, IMPLICATIONS, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In conclusion, the study's qualitative and quantitative findings highlighted the critical importance of empathy in achieving business success. Businesses were urged to invest in empathy-building initiatives, prioritize consumer feedback, and cultivate a culture of empathy and responsiveness. This approach would help them effectively navigate the dynamic social media landscape, positively influence consumer perceptions, and achieve sustainable growth. Recommendations included empathy training for business owners and employees, especially those managing social media interactions, implementing clear and accessible feedback channels, developing standardized response protocols, and viewing consumer feedback as a valuable source for continuous improvement. Fostering an organizational culture that prioritizes empathy was deemed essential for driving positive business outcomes. Emphasizing empathy in customer interactions could enhance customer satisfaction, loyalty, and brand reputation, leading to increased customer retention and differentiation in the market. Utilizing consumer feedback for ongoing improvements ensured businesses stayed attuned to evolving preferences and maintained long-term relevance. Overall, embracing empathy as a core value held significant potential for driving business growth, fostering loyalty, and ensuring sustained success in the competitive business landscape.

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